

Instructions for secure data processing in LTU Drive

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose

The purpose of this document is to describe the preventive security measures that should be undertaken and the recommendations that should be followed in order to ensure secure management of research data, when using LTU Drive. The document also aims to avoid any legal complications that might result from incorrect and insecure usage of LTU Drive. The document does not go into detail or presumes to explain how the researchers should act to implement the preventive security measures.

1.2 Target group

Internal and external parties who use LTU Drive as a storage solution for research data.

1.3 General instructions

Users of LTU Drive should have knowledge about how personal data should be managed, in accordance with GDPR and other relevant legal frameworks. The users should also work actively with information security, in the sense that research data must not be disclosed to unauthorized persons, distorted or be allowed to disappear.

External parties permanently stationed outside EU/EES are not part of LTU Drive's target audience, due to the difficulty of third country transfers of personal data.

Data that are subject to export control and data are regulated by the Protective Security Act¹ – research data that pertain to Sweden's national security – should not be store in LTU Drive.

All researchers are responsible for performing their work in accordance with good research practice. This includes contacting the university's various support functions, such as the legal office, archive or DAU.

In case of an information security incident, each individual researcher is responsible for reporting it to the relevant function within six hours of the incident. That is, contact IT in case of an IT security incident or the data protection officer in case of a personal data incident.

The use of multifactor authentication (MFA) is a criterium for logging into LTU Drive if the data in the storage space has a classification of C=2 or above. LTU recommends users to avoid unencrypted (open) networks when working with LTU Drive, as well as connect to their institution or organization's VPN. After every work session in LTU Drive, LTU recommends that the users actively log out of their accounts, so as to make use of the multifactor authentication's full functionality.

¹ SFS 2018:585 *Protective Security Act*

LTU recommends that all research projects use LTU Drive's pre-defined folder structure and adapt it to each project's specific needs.

LTU Drive should not be used as a substitute for other records and administrative systems. Which information that should be recorded in Platina, alternatively be stored in another administrative system, is defined in LTU's information management plans.

1.3.1 Preconditions for use of LTU Drive

- A research data classification has been conducted, approved by head of subject and received and recorded in Platina.
- A data management plan has been established and recorded in Platina.

1.4 Storage space in LTU Drive

Upon an approved application for storage space in LTU Drive, the project will be allocated a designated area where up to 1 TB of data can be stored. A project's storage space is provided with up to 500 GB of prepaid storage. The prepaid storage remains available as long as the project is active.

The project leader will be notified well in advance of the project's expected end date and the project's storage space must be closed in accordance with the established procedure.

1.4.1 Extra storage space

If additional storage beyond 500 GB is needed, the project can order extra storage space at a cost of 10 SEK per month for each new block of 100 GB. The cost is calculated monthly, which means it cannot be divided into a daily rate.

1.4.2 Research subject cost centre number

When applying, both a project number specific to the research project and a cost center for the responsible research subject must be provided. If a storage space in LTU Drive remains open after the end of a project, the research subject's cost center will be charged until the storage space is closed.

1.4.3 Data amounts exceeding 1 TB

If storage space is required for data amounts exceeding 1 TB, the project must place an order for a second, separate storage area. The storage area itself does not incur an additional cost, however, the project will be charged for the full amount of storage space it requires in the new storage area.

1.4.4 Responsibilities of the project leader

In addition to ordering storage space and potentially extra storage space, the following also applies:

- The project leader is responsible for doing inventory of which individuals should have access to the storage space.

- The project leader is responsible for shared files and folders, which includes renewing or removing shares, based on the current needs for access within the project.
- The project leader must make sure that the main folder is never shared with external parties. Shared folders should be situated as far down the folder structure's hierarchy as possible.
- The project leader should only use the ability to share files and folders in the storage spaces where they are project leaders.
- The project leader must make sure that the email containing the share link to maps and folders is encrypted so that it cannot be copied or forwarded. The following instructions must be added to the share email:

*“This email and its contents must not be forwarded
or otherwise shared with anyone but
the owner of this email address.”*

- The project leader must make sure that the addendum *LTU Drive: Addendum to research agreement* is signed by any external parties and is recorded in Platina together with the research or collaboration agreement.